

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE SELECTION OF CASSAVA PRODUCTS PROCESSED AMONG VALUE CHAIN ACTORS IN OGUN STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out in Ogun State to examine the factors influencing the selection of cassava products processed among value chain actors. Data collected from 160 respondents using the snowballing technique was analysed using frequencies, percentages and multinomial logistic regression analysis. The result of the study showed that the majority of the respondents processed into garri in the study area. The result further indicated that an increase in both the cost of cassava roots purchased, as well as the age of the processors increased the odds in favour of the selection of cassava flour and fufu compared to garri. The marginal effects of the processing technique used showed that using modern processing techniques resulted in 18% and 30.2% increases in the choice of cassava flour and fufu respectively, among the processors. The study concluded that there is cassava production inefficiency leading to the high cost of cassava tubers. It is also noted that the lack of modern equipment limited the participation and activities of some of the processors in the cause of processing into the selected products. The study recommended the need for interventions that will increase cassava production efficiency, thus, reducing both production costs and the price of cassava tubers at the farm gates and retail markets; it also suggested the production of affordable technologies which will be easily adopted by processors to encourage diversified engagements in the cassava value chain.

Keywords: *Processing techniques, Cassava products, Selection, Ogun State.*

INTRODUCTION

Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* L.) is a popular food crop, grown in many countries including Indonesia, Brazil, Thailand and several West African countries. Cassava is an important food crop with an annual output of over 34million tonnes of tuberous roots (Asogwa, 2013). Throughout the tropics, its roots and leaves provide essential calories and income. About 600 million people in Africa depend on cassava for food (International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD), 2013). It is largely produced by small-scale farmers using crude tools and most of the cassava produced is used for human consumption. As a food crop, cassava is planted mostly by smallholder farmers in Nigeria because it is available all

year round, therefore, ensuring household food security. Cassava is more tolerant to low soil fertility and more resistant to drought, pests and diseases (Obisesan, 2012). Its roots have the tendency of storing well in the ground for months after maturity (Ope-Ewe, 2011). In 2002, cassava gained national prominence after the pronouncement of a presidential initiative. The intent of the initiative was to use cassava as the engine of growth in Nigeria. The ability of any government to sustain agricultural production will depend to a great extent on the marketing of the farm produce. Production is only completed when product gets to the hands of the final consumer (Afolabi, 2012). Efficient marketing system stimulates agricultural production (Awoyinka

and Ikpi, 2015). The efficiency of any product is realized when the product is sold at prices higher than the production and distribution costs (Nwokoro, 2011). According to Afolabi (2012), agricultural development has been constrained by so many factors, one of which is marketing of commodities. Therefore, there is need to study the profitability of processing and marketing cassava.

The major objective of the study is to examine the factors influencing the selection of cassava products processed among value chain actors in Ogun State. The specific objectives of the study are to;

- a) describe the socio-economic characteristics of cassava processors in Ogun State
- b) investigate the unique methods of processing selected cassava products among the cassava processors in Ogun State.
- c) identify the factors determining the final products into which cassava is processed in Ogun State.

METHODOLOGY

Research Area

This study was carried out in Ogun State, Nigeria. Ogun State is a [state](#) in southwestern [Nigeria](#). It was created on the 3rd of February 1976 from the former [Western State](#). Ogun State borders [Lagos State](#) to the south, [Oyo State](#) and [Osun State](#) to the north, [Ondo State](#) to the east, and the Republic of [Benin](#) to the west. [Abeokuta](#) is both Ogun State's capital and most populous city; other important cities in the state include [Ijebu Ode](#), the royal capital of the [Ijebu Kingdom](#), and [Sagamu](#). The average rainfall in the state ranges between 1250 mm and 1800 mm with a slight bimodal rainfall distribution which peak in June and October while the dry season stretches from mid-November to mid-March. Temperature ranges from 24°C to 32°C and average relative humidity of 80% to 90%. Ogun state covers about 16,980.55 square kilometers.

Sources and Methods of Data Collection

The study made use of both primary and

secondary data. Primary data were sourced with the aid of a well-structured questionnaire and through oral interview to obtain required information from the respondents in the study area. Secondary data was sourced from articles and statistical publications.

Sampling techniques and sample size

Multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 160 respondents in the study area from the four Ogun State Agricultural Development Programme (OGADEP) zones. In the first stage, one local government was randomly selected from each of the Ogun State Agricultural Development Programme (OGADEP) zones, these local governments include Remo North, Ado-Odo/Ota, Odeda and Ogun Waterside. In the second stage, two communities that are predominantly involved in cassava processing were purposively selected from each of the local government areas giving eight communities which included Isara, Ipara, Igbesa, Itele, Opeji, Ijemo, Iwopin and Ibiade respectively. In the third stage, 20 respondents were selected from each of the communities using snowballing technique, giving a total of 160 respondents.

Method of Data Analysis

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse the data collected. The descriptive statistics (such as frequency tables and percentages) was used to describe the socio-economic variables (such as age, sex, marital status, educational level, household size, and working experience) and methods of processing cassava tubers. The inferential statistics (Multinomial Logistic Regression) was used to analyse the factors influencing the selection of cassava products.

Multinomial Logistic Regression Analysis

Multinomial logistic regression was used to analyse the factors determining the final products into which cassava is processed.

The multinomial logit model determines the probability that respondent *i* processed into one of *j* products of garri, cassava flour, fufu and starch. That probability is given by:

$$\ln \frac{\Pr(Y_i = k)}{\Pr(Y_i = K)} = \beta_k \cdot X_i, \quad k < K \quad (1)$$

$$\Pr(Y_i = k) = \Pr(Y_i = K) e^{\beta_k \cdot X_i}, \quad k < K \quad (2)$$

$$\Pr(Y_i = K) = \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^u e^{Z_j}} \quad (3)$$

where: $u = k-1$ and $Z_i = a + \beta_i X_i + e_t$

$$P_{ij} = \frac{e^{Z_i}}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^3 e^{Z_j}} \quad (4)$$

where:

$\Pr(Y_i = k)$ - Probability of the reference category (Garri)

P_{ij} - Probability of being in each of the groups compared to the reference group (Cassava flour, fufu and starch)

Y - Selection of processed cassava (1= cassava flour, 2 = fufu and 3= starch).

β_i - Set of estimated coefficients

X_i - Set of explanatory variables, which are:

X_1 - Cost of Cassava roots (₦/kg)

X_2 - Educational level of processor (years)

X_3 - Age of processor (years)

X_4 - Cost of labour (₦)

X_5 - Processing technique (modern processing technique=1, traditional processing technique=0)

X_6 - Cost of processing (₦)

X_7 - Distance to the market (km)

X_8 - Shelf life (Days)

X_9 - Source of labour (family labour=1, hired/exchange labour=0)

e_t - Disturbance term.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic Characteristics of the Respondents

Table 1 revealed that 8(5.0%) of the respondents were below 20years of age, 21(13.12%) were between 21 and 30 years of age, 45 (28.13%) were between 31 and 40 years of age, 56 (35.0%) were between the age of 41 and 50 while the remaining 30 (18.75%) of the respondents were above 50 years of age. The table further indicated that 33 (20.63%) of the respondents were male while the remaining 127(79.37%) of the respondents were female, meaning that, there were more female than male. The result on marital status showed that 105(65.62%) were married while others were single [7 (4.38%) not yet married, 15 (9.37%) divorced and 33 (20.63%) widowed]. Result

on educational attainment showed that 56 (35.0%) only had primary education, 40(25.0%) had secondary education, 32 (20.0%) had tertiary education, while the remaining 32 (20.0%) had no formal education. The result on respondents' working experience showed that 39(24.38%) of the respondents had 1-5 years of experience, 64(40.0%) had 6-10 years of experience, 35(21.87%) had 11-20 years of experience, while the remaining 22(13.75%) had more than 20 years of experience. The result on household size showed that 43(26.88%) of the respondents had between 1 and 5 household members, 95(59.37%) had between 6 and 10 household size, while the remaining 22 (13.75%) had more than 10 households size in the study area.

Table 1: Socio-economic Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Age (years)			
Below 20	8	5.0	47
21-30	21	13.12	
31-30	45	28.13	
41-50	56	35.0	
Above 50	30	18.75	
Sex			
Male	33	20.63	79.37
Female	127	79.37	
Marital Status			
Single	7	4.38	20.63
Married	105	65.62	
Divorced	15	9.37	
Widowed	33	20.63	
Educational Attainment			
Primary	56	35.0	20.0
Secondary	40	25.0	
Tertiary	32	20.0	
No Formal Edu.	32	20.0	
Working Experience (years)			
1-5	39	24.38	17
6-10	64	40.0	
11-20	35	21.87	
21 and above	22	13.75	
Household Size			
1-5	43	26.88	9
6-10	95	59.37	
11 and above	22	13.75	

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2023.

Processed Cassava Products

Cassava roots in the study area were processed into four different products which include garri, cassava flour, fufu and starch. It was observed that 82 (51.25%) of the respondents processed into Garri, 20(12.5%) processed

into cassava flour, 52(32.5%) processed into fufu, while the remaining 6 (3.75%) processed into starch. A conclusion can then be made that most of the respondents processed into garri in the study area.

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Respondents According to Processed Cassava Products

Products	Frequency	Percentage
Garri	82	51.25
Flour	20	12.5
Fufu	52	32.5
Starch	6	3.75
Total	160	100%

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2023.

Method of Processing into the Selected Cassava Products

* Method of Processing into Garri

There were three distinct processing methods or different stages in transforming cassava to garri product in the study area. These methods are basic, ordinary and premium methods. The basic method is depicted thus; Peeling-Washing-Grating-Dehydration-Frying, the ordinary method is Peeling-Washing-Grating-Dehydration-Fermentation-Frying, while the premium method is depicted as Peeling-Washing-Grating-Dehydration-Fermentation-Oiling-Frying.

The result showed that majority 47(57.32%) of the respondents adopted method '2' of the processing methods in the transformation of fresh cassava to garri. Meanwhile, 4(4.88%) of the respondents adopted method '1' in their processing of cassava to garri and 31(37.8%) of the respondents adopted method '3' in the transformation processes. This implies that majority of the respondents preferred processing method '2' to other processing methods as it has higher demand in the market by the consumers compared to other two methods

Method of Processing into Flour

There were three major processing methods in transforming cassava to flour product in the study area. The basic method is depicted thus; Peeling-Washing-Soaking-Sifting-Dewatering-Drying. While the ordinary method is depicted as Peeling-Washing-Soaking-Sifting-Dewatering-Drying-Milling and the premium method is Peeling-Washing-Soaking-Sifting-Dewatering-Molding-Drying-Milling.

The result showed that majority 14(70%) of the respondents adopted processing method '1' as their major practice in the study area. The implication of this is that, most of the respondents do not mill their dried molded cassava, before taking it to the market, hence, reduced white dusty powder. Meanwhile, 6(30%) of the respondents adopted method '3' while none of the respondents adopted method '2' in the transformation of fresh cassava to cassava flour.

Method of Processing into Fufu

There were three distinct processing methods of different stages in transforming cassava to fufu product in the study area. The basic method is depicted thus, Peeling-Washing-Soaking-Sifting-Dewatering-Boiling-

Molding. While the second method is depicted as Peeling-Washing-Soaking-Fermentation-Sifting-Dewatering-Boiling-Molding and the third method is Peeling-Washing-Soaking-Grinding-Fermentation-Sifting-Dewatering-Boiling-Molding.

The result showed that 41(78.85%) of the respondents adopted processing method '3' as the major method of transforming fresh cassava roots into fufu. Meanwhile 11(21.15%) of the respondents adopted processing method '2' in transforming the fresh cassava roots into fufu, while none of the respondents adopted processing method '1'. The reason for this was due to lack of fermentation in the processing method '1' hence reduction in the popular demand by the respondents because fermentation in the cassava processing method reduce or eliminate cyanide contents in fresh cassava roots which is harmful to human body. Hence, the processors adopted processing methods two and three.

Method of Processing into Starch

There were three major processing methods in transforming cassava to starch product in the study area. The basic method is depicted thus Peeling-Washing-Grinding-Sifting-Dewatering-Molding. While the ordinary method is depicted as Peeling-Washing-Grinding-Sifting-Dewatering-Molding-Drying-Blending and the premium method is Peeling-Washing-Soaking-Fermentation-Sifting-Dewatering-Molding. The result shows that all 6(100%) of the respondents adopted the ordinary processing method as their major practice in the transformation of fresh cassava roots to starch in the study area while none of them adopted method 1 and method 3.

The perception of using traditional method in processing cassava into the selected products is in agreement to that observed by Stella, Ikechi, and Lloyd (2013) in their study on processing and marketing of selected cassava products in South-east, Nigeria.

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of Methods of Processing the Selected Products

Methods	Frequency	Percentage
Garri		
Processing Method 1 (Basic)	4	4.88
Processing Method 2 (Ordinary)	47	57.32
Processing Method 3 (Premium)	31	37.8
Total	82	100%
Cassava flour		
Processing Method 1 (Basic)	14	70.0
Processing Method 2 (Ordinary)	0	0.0
Processing Method 3 (Premium)	6	30.0
Total	20	100%
Fufu		
Processing Method 1 (Basic)	0	0.0
Processing Method 2 (Ordinary)	11	21.15
Processing Method 3 (Premium)	41	78.85
Total	52	100%
Starch		
Processing Method 1 (Basic)	0	0.0
Processing Method 2 (Ordinary)	6	100.0
Processing Method 3 (Premium)	0	0.0
Total	6	100%

Source: Author's Field Survey, 2023.

Multinomial Logistic Regression Analyzing the Factors Determining the Final Products into which Cassava is Processed in Ogun State.

The results from this study showed that cost of cassava roots ($p < 0.01$), cost of labour ($p < 0.01$), processing technique ($p < 0.01$) and shelf life ($p < 0.05$) influence the selection of cassava flour compared to *garri* which is the baseline. Age of processor ($p < 0.05$), processing technique ($p < 0.01$) and shelf life ($p < 0.01$) influence the selection of *Fufu* while cost of labour ($p < 0.01$) and shelf life ($p < 0.01$) influence the selection of starch. The result further shows that 1% increase in cost of cassava roots will result to 4.39% increase in selection of cassava flour compared to *garri* while the marginal effects of age of processors shows that 1% increase in age will result to 6.1% increase in fufu selection compared to

garri. The implication is that, increase in both cost of cassava roots and age of processors resulted to increase in selection of cassava flour and fufu. The marginal effects of cost of labour shows that 1% increase in cost of labour will result to 4.2% and 9.6% decrease in selection of cassava flour and starch respectively. The implication is that increase in labour cost will reduce the selection of cassava flour and starch. The marginal effect of processing technique showed that the use of modern processing technique will result to 18% and 30.2% increase in selection of cassava flour and fufu respectively while the marginal effect of shelf life showed that 1% increase in shelf life will result to 1.7% and 19.9% increase in cassava flour and fufu selection but 3.02% increase in selection of starch.

Table 4: Multinomial Logistic Estimate of Factors Influencing the Selection of Cassava Product Processed in the Study Area.

Variable	Cassava flour		<i>Fufu</i>		Starch	
	Marginal effects	t-value	Marginal effects	t-value	Marginal effects	t-value
Cost of cassava roots	4.39E05***	3.8	-2.1E-05	0.03	-1.14E-10	0.99
Educational level	0.024	1.130	-0.036	-0.83	-4.52E-08	1.999
Age of processor	0.004	0.820	0.061**	2.1	-2.50E-08	1.000
Cost of labour	-4.2E05***	3.390	-2.2E-05	-0.17	-9.67E-12***	2.999
Processing technique	0.18***	0.000	0.302***	-2.69	2.02E-07	0.998
Cost of processing	-2.6E-05	-3.66	1.32E-05	0.13	3.19E-11	0.994
Distance to the market	0.016	0.580	-0.036	-0.92	3.85E-07	0.997
Shelf life	-0.017**	-2.200	-0.199***	-4.6	3.02E07***	2.995
Source of labour	-0.050	-0.930	-0.004	-0.3	6.63E-07	0.995
Diagnostic statistics						
LR chi ² (30)	157.600***					
Prob > chi ²	0.000***					
Pseudo R ²	0.452					
Log likelihood	-95.746					
Base outcome	Garri					

*** means significant at 1%

** means significant at 5%

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the processing of cassava roots into garri, cassava flour, fufu and starch in Ogun State. The results showed that there is cassava production inefficiency leading to high cost of cassava tubers at the farm gate and retail markets. It is also noted that lack of modern equipment limited the participation and activities of some of the processors in the cause of processing into the selected products.

The study recommended the need for interventions that will increase cassava production efficiency, thus, reducing both production costs and the price of cassava tubers at the farm gates and retail markets; it also suggested the need for government support in the provision of modern equipment at subsidized rate which will be easily adopted by processors in order to encourage diversified engagements in the cassava value chain.

REFERENCES

- Afolabi J.A. (2012). Assessment of the profitability of Garri marketing in Nigeria. *J. Applied Sci.*, 2, 4.
- Asogwa B.C., Ezihe J.A. and Ater P.I. (2013). Socio-economic analysis of cassava marketing in Benue State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovation and Applied Studies*, 2(4): 384-391.
- Awoyinka Y.A., and Ikpi A.E. (2015). Economics of Farm Income and Technical efficiency of Resources in Jigawa state industrial sugar cane project.
- International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) 2013. Cassava: Turning a Subsistence Crop into a Cash Crop in Western and Central Africa, Rural Poverty Portal, Bread crumbs Portlet, Powered by IFAD. From <http://www.fidafrique.net/rubrique554.html> (Retrieved on 27 June 2013).
- Nwokoro, J.A. (2011). Assessment of the profitability of Garri marketing in Nigeria. *J. Applied Sci.*, Vol.2 No. 4
- Obisesan A. (2013). Credit accessibility and poverty among smallholder cassava farming households in southwest Nigeria. *Greener Journal of Agricultural Sci.*, 3(2):120-127.
- Ope-Ewe O.B., Adetunji M.O., Kafiyah M.R., Onadipe O.O., Awoyale W., Alenkhe B.E. and Sanni L.O. (2011). Cassava Value Chain Development by Supporting Processing and Value Addition by Small and Medium Enterprises in West Africa – Nigeria. *Technical Report August 2008 – August 2011*.
- Stella O. Ani, Ikechi K. Agbugbal and Lloyd J.S. and Baiyegunhi (2013). Processing and Marketing of Selected Cassava Products in South-east Nigeria. *J Economics*, 4(2): 105-111 (2013).
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